

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND BIOCOMPATIBILITY OF FUNCTIONALIZED CARBON NANOTUBES FILLED POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITES FOR ORTHOPEDIC BONE IMPLANTS APPLICATION

Jing Ma¹, and Xi Nan

¹Research institute of Surface Engineering, Taiyuan University of Technology
Taiyuan, China
Email: majing@tyut.edu.cn

Keywords: biocompatibility, Carbon nanotubes, functionalization, mechanical properties, polypropylene

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the efficiency of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) as reinforcement for polypropylene (PP) for orthopedic bone implants application as a function of different surface functionalization of carbon nanotube. PP composites were reinforced using various CNTs: single- and multiwalled carbon nanotubes (SWNTs, MWNTs), the CNTs were functionalized by covalent and noncovalent methods, SWNTs were covalently functionalized by plasma and grafted with the COOH and NH₂ groups respectively, for comparison, the MWNTs were functionalized noncovalently by biomacromolecules (lysozyme and chitosan). The different CNTs were incorporated into PP by injection molding techniques. PP was used as the baseline control, mechanical testing and biocompatibility testing was measured on the PP polymer and composites. It was found that, the type of CNTs and surface functionalization affects the mechanical and biocompatibility results significantly. The results also indicated that the extent of mechanical reinforcement is closely dependent on the dispersion of CNTs. Hansen solubility parameters method and Confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) were employed to analysis the dispersion of CNTs in PP polymer matrix. The analysis of XPS and Raman spectroscopy of the nanostructures taken together with the above results indicated differences in nanostructure and the chemical compositions, number of functional groups, and structural defects for the CNTs may be key factors affects the mechanical properties and biocompatibility of PP nanocomposites compared to the controls. The suitable CNTs and surface functionalization of CNTs were selected for making the PP/CNTs orthopedic bone implants.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since Japanese scientist Iijima discovered carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in 1991^[1], carbon nanotubes have caught great attention owing to their superior and unique structural, mechanical, electrical, thermal properties^[2-5], and they have been used in many applications such as high-strength, highly conducting composite materials^[6-9], sensors^[10, 11], solar cells^[12], hydrogen storage^[13], supercapacitors^[14], drug delivery and cancer therapy^[15] and so on.

Carbon nanotube (CNT) is a special kind of material with long, hollow cylindrical nanostructure and formed by rolling graphene layers. According to the number of graphene layer, CNTs can be categorized as single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). Diameter distribution range of SWCNTs is relatively smaller than MWCNTs, so they possess higher aspect ratio. Consequently, SWCNTs have a higher tendency to agglomerate than MWCNTs. In addition, the strong van der Waals force and π - π stacking between CNTs given rise to the agglomerate and entanglement of CNTs, which limited the application of carbon nanotubes on other fields. Therefore, the dispersion of CNTs became one of the most important research subjects. As we all know, many methods have been applied to disperse CNTs, including physical methods and chemical methods. Physical methods contain grind, ultrasonic treatment, magnetic stirring, etc.

Chemical methods are comprised of covalently modification and non-covalent modification.

Covalent modification is to achieve the connection of covalent bond between the modified group and CNTs by changing the sp^2 hybridization of carbon atoms or damaging π -electron conjugated system between CNTs^[16-18]. Many experiments have been conducted to functionalize covalently CNTs with amidogen, carboxyl and other functional groups. In 2008, Zois Syrgiannis et.al^[18] surveyed that SWCNTs was covalently functionalized by lithium n-propylamide and the results demonstrated that the solubility of the propylamine-functionalized SWCNTs was drastically increased in organic solvents. In 2015, Florence pennetreau et.al^[17] covalently functionalized CNTs with seven different xanthates and peroxides as radical initiators (one-step double functionalization). The results demonstrated that the maximum grafting of the xanthates was simply a function of quantity of peroxide introduced to the reaction, when the xanthates and peroxide were introduced in stoichiometric amounts. Accordingly, covalently functionalized CNTs with amidogen and carboxyl can effectively improve its solubility in solvents.

Non-covalent modification method is to make π electrons between CNTs and the other organic molecules form π - π stacking, that is to say, this method not only preserves the original structure of CNTs but also achieves the functionalization of CNTs^[19-24]. Generally, CNTs can be functionalized noncovalently by surfactants, polymers, biomacromolecules, etc. In 2012, Ke zhang's groups^[19] prepared the core-shell structured snowman-like (SL) microparticles coated by functionalized MWCNT in the presence of different surfactants including cationic surfactant-cetyl trimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and anionic surfactant-sodium lauryl sulfate(SDS). They found that the cationic surfactant is more effective than an anionic surfactant, inducing much more uniform MWCNT -COOH incorporation to SL particles. In 2013, Eun Yub Choi^[20] et al. functionalized MWCNTs using pyrene derivatives (PBC), the PBC-MWCNTs were melt mixed with PA66 using a twin extruder. Finally, they found that PBC-MWCNTs exhibited the best interfacial adhesion between MWCNTs and PA66 matrix and highest-level dispersion in PA66 matrix. In 2014, Cuiyun Li et.al synthesized the MWCNTs-chitosan hybrids on Ti substrate by the electrophoretic deposition (EDP) process. And the results demonstrated that the EPD-enabled nanostructured CNT-Chi hybrid coatings may be potentially useful as the cell-stimulating and therapeutic interfaces of metallic implants, for bone repair and regeneration. In our study, we aimed to noncovalently functionalize MWCNTs with chitosan(CS), and the functionalized MWCNTs were added into PP to form PP/CS/MWCNTs composites. Dispersion, mechanical property, and biocompatibility of PP/CS/MWCNTs were investigated to address PP potential usefulness as bone implants. Therefore, non-covalent method also can change the dispersion of carbon nanotubes sharply.

Furthermore, many computing methods and charactering instruments have been employed in studying accurately the dispersibility and degree of functionalization of CNTs, for example, Hansen solubility parameter (HSP)^[25-27], Dynamic light scattering (DLS), Ultraviolet and visible spectrophotometer (UV-Vis), Raman spectroscopy, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier transformed infrared (FTIR)^[28-34] etc. Among these means, HSP is a kind of efficient mean forecasting solubility between a material and solvent. In three-dimensional space, the HSP of a solvent represents the center of sphere, and the radius stands for the maximum tolerance of the solvent. Therefore, for CNTs, miscible solvent is within the sphere and immiscible solvent is out of the sphere.

When researchers studied the dispersibility of CNTs, they gradually expanded their research topic to polymer field. In this field, CNTs have two applications: on the one hand, as reinforcements, CNTs is used to improve the mechanical, electrical, thermal, biological properties of polymer materials^[35-44]. On the other hand, CNTs were functionalized or modified by polymers^[45-49]. Of all polymers, owing to the low cost, excellent plastic toughness and high light transmission, polypropylene (PP) is widely applied to construction, medical treatment, appliance and automotive parts, chemical and other industries. However, PP has low strength and hardness, making it unable to serve as loaded parts. Thus, many researchers regarded CNTs as nanofillers and added it to the PP with the purpose of improving

mechanical properties and biocompatibility of PP.

In this work, firstly, we used biological macromolecules (chitosan and lysozyme) to functionalize the MWCNTs in a noncovalent way. Secondly, we compared and analyzed systematically the solubility of the three MWCNTs (MWCNTs, CS/MWCNTs composite, and LZ/MWCNTs composite) with three SWCNTs (SWCNTs, plasma-COOH functionalized SWCNTs, and plasma-NH₂ functionalized SWCNTs) in different solvent by using Ultraviolet and visible spectrophotometer (UV-Vis) and Dynamic light scattering (DLS), respectively. And then the six kinds of CNTs were added into PP, and the mechanical properties of pp composites were characterized by tensile test. The impact of different CNTs on the mechanical properties of PP nanocomposites was investigated by comparing and analyzing systematically the dispersion of CNTs in PP employing confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM). Finally, bone cell proliferation experiments were conducted on these specimens, analyzing their biocompatibility.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The SWCNTs, plasma-COOH functionalized SWCNTs, and plasma-NH₂ functionalized SWCNTs used in this study were purchased from Cheaptubes Company and synthesized by thermal chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method.

The MWCNTs used in this study were purchased from XFNANO Company (Nanjing, China) and synthesized by thermal chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method. The nanotubes XFM13 are with length 10-30 μ m, outer diameter 10-20nm, and average surface area more than 200 m²/g, and purity higher than 95% without functionalization.

The lysozyme and chitosan were purchased from China Shanghai Ruji biotechnology limited company. The PP (PPH-T03) used in this study were purchased from SINOPEC Maoming Company.

The chitosan functionalized CNTs were prepared by three steps. Firstly, 100ml of 2% acetic solution was prepared by using 98% acetic. Secondly, chitosan of 250mg were added into the 2% acetic solution to form a chitosan-acetic solution, and then MWCNTs of 100mg were poured into the chitosan-acetic solution, which was sonicated by SONICS VCX800 by a power at 160W for 30min. The mixture was sealed in preservation bags and shaken by a constant temperature water bath oscillator (WHY-2, Jingyuguosheng Experimental Instrument Factory, Jiangsu Jintan) under 100rpm at 37°C for 3h. Afterwards, the mixture was centrifuged at a speed of 7500rpm for 30 min using a high speed freezing centrifuge (KDC-140HR, Anhui Zhongke Zhongjia Science Instrument Co. Ltd.) to collect the upper uniform dispersed suspension. 2ml upper liquid was took out for the Fourier infrared test indicated that the chitosan coated MWCNTs. Eventually, the chitosan wrapped MWCNT film (CS/MWCNTs) was obtained by drying the residual uniform dispersions in an oven at 60°C for 24h.

The lysozyme functionalized CNTs were prepared by the following steps: firstly, 200mg lysozyme was added into 200ml phosphate buffer solution (PBS) forming uniform lysozyme-PBS solution. And then 200mg MWCNTs were poured into the above solution, which was sonicated by SONICS VCX800 by a 160W for 30min to form suspension. Secondly, the mixture was shaken under 100rpm at 37°C for 3h and centrifuged at the speed of 6000rpm for 15min, and the precipitate was washed using 10ml PBS each time (washed repeatedly for 5 times) to clean the unwrapped lysozyme. Eventually, the lysozyme wrapped MWCNT powder (LZ/MWCNTs) were acquired by drying the precipitate in an oven at 60°C for 24h.

2.2 Preparation of Composites

PP composites were fabricated by solution blending method. Firstly, xylene of 50ml was ultrasonically mixed with CNTs of 100mg for 45min, and the sonicator (SONICS VCX800) was set at

160W. Secondly, 50g of PP were added into 50ml xylene and stirred at 135°C until PP were dissolved. Thirdly, the mixture xylene-CNTs solution was poured slowly into PP solution, which was stirred by using standard overhead type electronic blender (OS20-S, Dragon xingchuang experiment instrument co., LTD) for 30 min. Furthermore, the compounds were heated at 110°C for 48h to remove xylene. It is worth noting that the MWCNTs/CS is dissolved in the same volume 2% acetic solution, and then the subsequent steps is the same as previous steps to fabricate other PP composites. Injection molding was carried out at 170~260°C, holding at 0.5MPa for 5s.

2.3 Experimental Methods

2.3.1 Raman

The functionalization of SWCNTs was characterized by a Raman spectrometer (Renishaw Invia Raman Microscope) to find the structural change of the SWCNTs, using He-Ne laser (632.8nm) focusing $\times 50$ objective lens on the sample.

2.3.2 X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

The functional degree of the SWCNTs was analyzed by an ESCALAB 250 XPS instrument, which is produced by Thermo Fisher Scientific with a high-resolution spectrometer. The instrument employed monochromatic Al K α 200W as the X-ray source and formed a spot size of 500 μ m on the sample. For the overall survey, pass energies of 200eV was used. The lens mode was set to Large Area XL, and the analyzer mode was Constant Analyzer Energy during analysis.

2.3.3 FTIR

The functionalization of MWCNTs, chitosan-MWCNTs and lysozyme-MWCNTs were analysed by Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) (BRUKER TENSOR 27), wavenumber range was from 400 cm^{-1} to 4000 cm^{-1} . KBr of 50mg and very small amount of MWCNTs and lysozyme-MWCNTs were mixed and ground with a mortar, and then pressed into a flat flake. The chitosan-MWCNTs solution was dropped onto the flat flake manufactured by 50mg KBr, and dried with air dryer, to test the FTIR of the sample of chitosan-MWCNTs composite.

2.3.4 XRD

The functionalization of MWCNTs, chitosan-MWCNTs and lysozyme-MWCNTs were analysed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) (DX2700, Dandong Liaoning, with Cu target and K α ray) ($\lambda=0.15406$). The scanning angle is from 10 to 80°.

2.3.5 Hansen solubility parameters experiments

Hansen solubility parameter (HSP) is an effective method investigating the solubility and dispersibility of one material in solvents. In three-dimensional space, the Hansen solubility

Parameters D, P, and H represent dispersion forces, dipolar interactions, and hydrogen bonding, respectively. The HSPs of a solute represent the center of the HSP sphere, and the radius of this sphere, R₀, indicates the maximum tolerance of the solution. Therefore, miscible solvent are include within the sphere and immiscible solvent are out of the sphere.

To evaluate the HSPs of the SWCNTs, the DLS was implemented to characterize the hydrodynamic size of SWCNTs in 20 different solvents after tip sonication, the experiments and results was reported in previous work^[16].

2.3.5.1 Determine Hansen solubility parameters of MWCNTs in 23 kinds of different solvent

For the MWCNTs, 1mg MWCNTs was put into 23 kinds of different solvents of 4ml, which was sonicated at 160W for 2min. And in order to get the mixture contained 25ug/ml of CNTs, the solution was diluted 100 times and sonicated for 2min. Next, 4ml of the mixture solution were put into the glass cell to test the absorbance at 600 nm by using the UV-Vis spectrophotometry (UV-1800PC, Meipuda, Shanghai). The glass cell was in a static state and recorded absorbance at intervals of half hour (the test last for three hours). The first absorbance was recorded as A1, and the second absorbance was A2, and so on. Settlement percentage (SP) can be calculated, the function of which is as follows:

$$SP=(A_i(2,3,4,5,6,7)-A_1)/A_1 \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Linear fit the line chart of these settlement percentage values was drew out and the slope represented sedimentation rate of 23 different solvents can be calculated. When the slope is large which means the sedimentation speed is fast and the dispersion of MWCNTs are very poor, oppositely, when the slope is small, the solvent for the MWCNTs is good solvents.

2.3.5.2 Determine Hansen solubility parameters of CS/MWCNTs in 23 kinds of different solvent

CS/MWCNTs film of 23 mg was dissolved in 23ml of 2% acetic solution and sonicated for 15min, then the solution was divided equally into 23 vials (each vial is 1ml). These vials was dry at 60°C for 48h. Next, 23 different solvents (each solvent is 4ml) were poured into these vials, respectively. And these mixture solutions were sonicated using the sonicator at 160W for 5min and sonicated again with ultrasonic bath for 1h. Eventually, the absorbance was recorded by the UV-Vis spectrophotometry at 600 nm. Of all these absorbance, the large absorbance is in accord with the good solvent for CS/MWCNTs. On the contrary, the small absorption is in accord with the bad solvent.

2.3.5.3 Determine Hansen solubility parameters of LZ/MWCNTs in 23 kinds of different solvent

LZ/MWCNTs of 1mg was put into 23 kinds of different solvents (each solvent is 4ml) and sonicated at 160W for 2min. And so as to get the mixture contained 2.5mg/ml of carbon nanotubes the solution was diluted 10 times and sonicated for 2min. Finally, the absorbance was recorded by the same method as CS/MWCNTs.

2.3.6 Dispersion of CNTs

The dispersion of CNTs in PP was analyzed by confocal laser scanning microscopy (NikonC2 plus, ShanHai) on thin composite sections, which were ground from the dog bone specimens with a thickness of 0.4-0.5mm.

2.3.7 Mechanical testing

The mechanical property of PP nanocomposites was measured using a tensile testing machine with strain rate of 5mm/min. The reported E modulus and tensile strength were the average values of three samples.

2.3.8 Biocompatibility testing

The specimens with a dimension of 15×10×2mm were cut from the dog bone specimens. Prior to the cell cultivation, the specimens were sterilized with 75% ethanol and rinsed thoroughly with sterile phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). And dimethyl thiazolyl diphenyl tetrazolium (MTT) colorimetric assay was performed to determine the cell viability of the PP and PP composites. The cell suspension of 100cm² with 2×10⁴ cells was seeded on each specimen with a dimension of 15×10×2mm placed in a 24-well plate and incubated at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere for 12h. Finally, these specimens

were washed by PBS and the cell was dyed with LIVE/DEAD at room temperature for 40min. Afterwards, wash the specimens with PBS again. Finally, the live and dead conditions of the cells were observed by the confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Functionalization of carbon nanotubes

3.1.1 Covalent functionalization of SWCNTs

Figure.1 showed the Raman spectra of the as received SWCNTs and functionalized SWCNTs with COOH and NH₂. Meanwhile, the information of the structure change caused by covalent functionalization was also given in Figure.1. The feature peak at around 1300 cm⁻¹ is “D band” because of the defects on the nanotube surface, while the feature peak at around 1580 cm⁻¹ is called “G band” due to the existence of graphite structure. The ratio of the intensity between D and G band is I_D/I_G, which can be used to evaluate the degree of the functionalization by covalent defects.

The I_D/I_G of plasma COOH and plasma NH₂ functionalized SWCNTs increased significantly compared to the as received SWCNTs, which gave the evidence of the covalent functionalization. Therefore, the functional degree of the plasma COOH SWCNTs is higher than the plasma NH₂ SWCNTs due to higher I_D/I_G values.

Figure 1: Raman spectra of different SWCNTs

Table 1 provided the atomic content of the SWCNTs and functionalized SWCNTs with COOH and NH₂ by XPS analysis. The information of the functional degree of the SWCNTs can also be given by the elemental analyses of XPS. It had higher oxygen content of 12.8% for the plasma carboxylic acid functionalized SWCNTs than that of the as received SWCNTs (2.8%), which was the proof of the COOH groups. The nitrogen content increased to 2.3% indicating that the amine groups connected on the SWCNTs surface. In addition, the oxygen content of the plasma amine functionalized SWCNTs increased to 5.2% compared to that of the SWCNTs, which may be because the absorbed water on the SWCNTs participated in the reaction during plasma treatment.

Materials	Cl _{1s}	O _{1s}	N _{1s}	Cl _{2p}	F _{1s}
SWCNTs	96.1	2.8		0.2	0.9
Plasma COOH SWCNTs	87.2	12.8			
Plasma NH ₂ SWCNTs	90.6	5.2	2.3	0.4	1.6

Table 1: Atomic content of different SWCNTs by XPS

3.1.2 Non-covalent functionalization of MWCNTs

FTIR can be used to analyse the functionalization of CNTs. FTIR spectra of different MWCNTs are shown in Figure. 2. Peaks at around 1640cm⁻¹ and 3441cm⁻¹ are connected with carboxyl and hydroxyl groups [29], respectively, which are caused by oxidization in ambient atmospheric on the surface of MWCNTs.

The IR spectrum of CS/MWCNTs^[50] had a broad peak at 2928cm⁻¹, which is assigned to the vibration of CH₂. In addition, the feature band due to CH₂ scissoring, which usually occurs at 1395cm⁻¹ is also present in this spectrum. Moreover, the C=O stretching of amide I bond is observed at 1697-1724cm⁻¹, which usually occurs in the range of 1600-1700cm⁻¹, and strong N-H bending vibration of amide II occurred at 1632cm⁻¹, which usually occurs in the range of 1550-1640cm⁻¹ as strong band. Of these peaks, the peak of amide I and amide II are the characteristic band of amino group which was contained by chitosan. Therefore, the peak of amide I and amide II indicated that the free CS coated on the MWCNTs surface. However, for the lysozyme functionalized MWCNTs, because only very small amount of lysozyme attached onto the MWCNTs, the functional groups cannot be detected by FTIR technique.

Figure 2: FTIR of different MWCNTs

The XRD spectra of Chitosan/MWCNTs and Lysozyme/MWCNTs hybrid and as received MWCNTs were shown Figure.3. In the case, crystalline phases of MWCNTs were at 26.2 °, 43.1 ° and 54.7 °. For the Chitosan/MWCNTs, the peak at 21 ° represented the chitosan crystallization^[34]. And the spectra peaks become broaden and many noise peaks appears because the amorphous chitosan wrapped onto the MWCNTs surface. It also demonstrated that the chitosan has attached onto the MWCNTs surface. For the Lysozyme/MWCNTs, the typical crystal peaks of lysozyme were at around

31.72 ° and 45.55 °^[51]. Meanwhile, the peaks of Lysozyme/MWCNTs contained also characteristic peaks of the MWCNTs, which shown that the lysozyme attached on MWCNTs surface.

Figure 3: XRD of different MWCNTs

3.2 Dispersion of Carbon nanotubes

3.2.1 In solvents

The dispersion of three different SWCNTs in 20 different solvents was studied in the author's previous work^[16]. In this work, we studied the dispersion of three different MWCNTs in 23 different solvents. Based on the deposition rate or the absorption of the CNTs solution after sonication, the solubility of the nanotubes can be judged as 0 or 1 ('0' stands bad solvent, '1' stands good solvent). The information of deposition rate and the absorption of the CNTs solution after sonication were given in Table 2.

Vertical perspective, firstly, the solubility of MWCNTs is characterized by its deposition rate (DRE). The small DRE means the good solubility for MWCNTs and vice versa. Therefore, we found that acetyl acetone showed the best solubility, while tetrachloroethylene showed the worst solubility. Secondly, as to CS/MWCNTs and LZ/MWCNTs, their absorption (A) after sonication represents their solubility. The large A signifies the good solubility and vice versa. We found that, for CS/MWCNTs, decahydronaphthalene was the best solvent, while chloroform was the worst solvent. For LZ/MWCNTs, ethanediol is the best solvent, while hexane is the worst solvent.

Horizontal comparison, firstly, the methanol and water is bad solvent for MWCNTs, while it is good solvent for CS/MWCNTs and LZ/MWCNTs, which may because the chitosan or lysozyme coated MWCNTs surface compatible with them. In addition, the ethylacetate and decahydronaphthalene turned the good solvent when use the CS coated MWCNTs and the reason is the same as above.

The SWCNTs, the COOH plasma-treated SWNTs and NH₂ plasma-treated SWNTs was only dispersed well in DMF, so the HSP of the SWCNTs, the COOH plasma-treated SWNTs and NH₂ plasma-treated SWNTs are the same as dimethylformamide (DMF), and the radius of the HSP sphere was negligibly small and regarded as zero, only the hydrodynamic sizes of the nanotubes are different^[16]. Therefore, we believed that SWCNTs, the COOH plasma-treated SWNTs and NH₂ plasma-treated SWNTs was almost non-dispersant well in solvents and materials expect DMF.

The HSP data of three different MWCNTs (MWCNTs, CS/MWCNTs and LZ/MWCNTs) were calculated by a computer software we designed, and the HSP data were showed in Table 3. In order to see their location and size clearly, basing on the data of Table 3, the HSPs spheres of three different MWCNTs were drew by the our software, which were showed in Figure 4. Among those, the radius and the centre of the sphere for three MWCNTs is different, and the radius of CS/MWCNTs and LZ/MWCNTs was larger than that of MWCNTs, which illustrated that noncovalently functionalized MWCNTs with chitosan and lysozyme changed MWCNTs dispersibility and dissolving capacity. In addition, the radius of CS/MWCNTs was larger than LZ/MWCNTs, which indicated that the CS/MWCNTs can be well dispersed in more solvents than LZ/MWCNTs.

No	Solvent	Solubility of MWCNTs	Deposition rate of MWCNTs	Solubility of CS/MWCNTs	Absorption of CS/MWCNTs after ultrasound	Solubility of LZ/MWCNTs	Absorption of LZ/MWCNTs after ultrasound
1	Methanol	0	0.069	1	0.033	1	0.232
2	Ethanol	1	0.013	1	0.037	0	0.040
3	2-propanol	1	0.002	1	0.031	1	0.481
4	Acetone	1	0.001	0	0.000	0	0.022
5	Tetrahydrofuran	1	0.005	0	0.000	0	0.028
6	Cyclohexanone	1	0.006	1	0.031	0	0.057
7	Ethyl acetate	0	0.088	1	0.021	0	0.024
8	Toluene	1	0.016	1	0.130	0	0.015
9	DMF	1	0.009	0	0.000	1	0.070
10	Triethylamine	1	0.002	1	0.063	0	0.008
11	Dicloromethane	0	0.044	0	0.000	0	0.024
12	Tetrachloromethane	1	0.015	0	0.000	0	0.013
13	Hexane	0	0.139	0	0.000	0	0.000
14	Chloroform	1	0.027	0	0.000	0	0.010
15	Decahydronaphthalene	0	0.173	1	0.997	0	0.027
16	Xylol	1	0.023	1	0.053	0	0.028
17	Tetrachloroethylene	0	0.256	0	0.017	0	0.015
18	Benzene	0	0.032	0	0.000	0	0.000
19	Water	0	0.005	1	0.050	1	0.459
20	N-butyl alcohol	1	0.002	0	0.000	1	0.134
21	Ethenediol	1	0.008	1	0.010	1	0.611
22	Acetylacetone	1	0.002	0	0.000	0	0.070
23	1-2-propylene glycol	1	0.010	1	0.032	1	0.249

Table 2: Hansen solubility parameters and UV-Vis experimental results

	D	P	H	Ro
MWCNT	20.8	2.9	13.5	14.5
CS/MWCNT	-2.1	-13.3	25.4	48.8
LZ/MWCNT	4.8	18.5	23.7	28.5

Table 3: HSPs of MWCNTs, CS/MWCNTs and LZ/MWCNTs

Figure 4: HSP sphere of MWCNTs, CS/MWCNTs and LZ/MWCNTs (Blue sphere is MWCNTs gray sphere is CS/MWCNTs and yellow sphere is LZ/MWCNTs)

3.2.2 In polypropylene Matrix

PP has a good light transmittance, so confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) with transmission light is applicable to characterize the agglomerates of CNTs. The dispersion of six kinds of CNTs in the PP matrix was evaluated by CLSM as shown in Figure 5.

Horizontally compared PP/MWCNTs and PP/SWCNTs, PP/MWCNTs was more homogeneously black than PP/SWCNTs, in the PP/SWCNTs, there are many had aggregations not easy to break, which may be attributed to MWCNTs was dispersed well in xylene after sonication, while the xylene was not the best solvent for SWCNTs.

Among PP/MWCNTs, PP/CS/MWCNTs and PP/LZ/MWCNTs composites, the number and area of aggregations of PP/CS/MWCNTs and PP/LZ/MWCNTs was less than PP/MWCNTs, which may be ascribed to noncovalently functionalized MWCNTs improved dispersion of the MWCNTs. The results were in accordance with HSPs results (Figure 4). In addition, we observed that the dark spot of PP/CS/MWCNTs is smaller and distributed more uniform than PP/LZ/MWCNTs, which may be put down to the xylene was not the best solvent for LZ/MWCNTs (Table 2) and the maximum tolerance capacity of LZ/MWCNTs was smaller than that of CS/MWCNTs (Figure 4).

Among PP/SWCNTs, PP/COOH-SWCNTs and PP/NH₂-SWCNTs, the number and area of the dark spot of PP/SWCNT composites was larger than PP/COOH-SWCNT and PP/NH₂-SWCNT, which may be attributed to the dispersion of functionalized covalently SWCNTs was better than one of SWCNTs. What's more, we aware of the black field of PP/COOH-SWCNTs was more uniform than PP/NH₂-SWCNTs, and the dark spot of PP/COOH-SWCNTs was the smaller and distributed more uniform than PP/NH₂-SWCNT, which is attributed to the degree of functionalization of SWCNTs with carboxylic acid is higher than that of amino group. This is in accordance with the results of XPS (Table 1).

Among all of PP composites, we observed that the dispersion of PP/SWCNTs is the worst, which may be ascribed to the SWCNTs was more easy to agglomerate than other CNTs, while the dispersion of PP/CS/MWCNTs is the best, which may be attributed to the acetic acid is the best solvent for CS/MWCNTs. In addition, the compatibility between PP and LS/MWCNTs is not good as CS/MWCNTs.

Figure 5: The dispersion of six kinds of CNTs in the PP matrix was evaluated by CLSM (a) PP/MWCNTs, (b) PP/CS/MWCNTs, (c) PP/LZ/MWCNTs, (d) PP/SWCNTs, (e) PP/SWCNTs-COOH, (f) PP/SWCNTs-NH₂ (Dark spot represents the aggregate particles of CNTs, white represents the PP matrix)

3.3 Mechanical properties

The E modulus and tensile strength of PP/CNTs composites were shown in Table 4. The mechanical testing could reflect the homogeneity and interfacial adhesion between the CNTs nanofillers and the PP matrix in some extent.

We can clearly draw the conclusion that the tensile strength of PP with CNTs is higher than pure PP, which may be attributed to the outstanding mechanical properties of CNTs strengthen the PP in some way. Besides, compared PP/SWCNT with PP/MWCNT, we found that generally PP/SWCNT exhibited the higher tensile strength than PP/MWCNT, which may be put down to better interfacial adhesion between SWCNTs and PP.

PP/MWCNT, PP/CS/MWCNT and PP/LZ/MWCNT composites, we can observe that the E modulus of PP/CS/MWCNT and PP/LZ/MWCNT was higher than that one of PP/MWCNT (44.16% and 15.11%, respectively), while the tensile strength of PP/CS/MWCNT and PP/LZ/MWCNT was slightly decreased by 0.96% and 0.96%, respectively. The results were caused by the good dispersion of functionalized MWCNTs in PP, which was in accord with Figure 5. In addition, The E modulus of PP/CS/MWCNT was 25.23% higher than that one of PP/LZ/MWCNT, while the tensile strength of PP/CS/MWCNT was barely decreased. The results may be attributed to the larger maximum tolerance capacity of PP/CS/MWCNT (Figure 4), which caused the better dispersion of PP/CS/MWCNT than PP/LZ/MWCNT in PP (Figure 5)

Compared PP/SWCNTs with PP/COOH-SWCNTs and PP/NH₂-SWCNTs, we found that the E modulus of PP/COOH-SWCNTs and PP/NH₂-SWCNTs decreased by 8.03% and 31.60%, respectively. These results were attributed to the defects caused by covalent functionalization of SWCNTs.

Compare PP/SWCNTs with PP/COOH-SWCNTs, the tensile strength of PP/COOH-SWCNTs slightly decreased by 0.68%. Compare PP/SWCNTs with PP/NH₂-SWCNTs, the tensile strength of PP/NH₂-SWCNTs sharply increased by 1.54%. These results are due to the defects caused by covalent functionalization of SWCNTs and the degree of functionalization of COOH-SWCNTs was higher than NH₂-SWCNTs (Figure 1 and Table 1). In addition, The E modulus of PP/COOH-SWCNTs was 25.62% higher than that one of PP/NH₂-SWCNTs, which may be put down to the dispersion of PP/COOH-SWCNTs was better than PP/NH₂-SWCNTs(Figure 5). While the tensile strength of PP/COOH-SWCNTs barely decreased by 2.24%. The results may be attributed to the defects caused by covalent functionalization of SWCNTs and the degree of functionalization of COOH-SWCNTs was higher than NH₂-SWCNTs. (Figure 1 and Table 1).

From the Table 4, we observed that the PP/CS/MWCNTs nanocomposites shown the largest E modulus, while the PP/NH₂-SWCNTS exerted the smallest young's modulus, which may due to the destruction and defects of SWCNTs caused by covalent functionalization and the noncovalent functionalization did not cause defects.

Sample	E modulus	Tensile strength(MPa)
PP	131.59 ± 3.49	32.74 ± 1.58
PP/MWCNT	115.57 ± 2.54	34.43 ± 1.04
PP/CS/MWCNT	166.60 ± 19.52	34.10 ± 1.44
PP/LZ/MWCNT	133.03 ± 26.09	33.10 ± 1.80
PP/SWCNT	141.52 ± 10.60	35.54 ± 1.45
PP/COOH-SWCNT	130.15 ± 14.84	35.30 ± 1.21
PP/NH ₂ -SWCNT	96.80 ± 2.74	36.09 ± 0.84

Table 4: Tensile strength and E modulus of the PP nanocomposites

3.4 Biocompatibilities

Figure 6 shows the CLSM micrographs of pure PP cultivated with osteoblasts for 12h. Due to the toxicity of CNTs, the biocompatibility of between CNTs and PP decreased sharply. Thus, to judge the biocompatibility of PP/CNTs making the orthopedic bone implants, we focused on conducting dimethyl thiazolyl diphenyl tetrazolium (MTT) colorimetric assay. We found that no cells can be observed on samples of PP/ SWCNT, PP/COOH-SWCNT and PP/LZ/MWCNT, which may because the these samples with carbon nanotuebs had very strong toxicity on osteoblasts cell and the affinity and biocompatibility between PP and CNTs was weak. Compared the PP composites with osteoblasts cells attached, we observed that the number of live cells on pure PP was more than one of on the PP/ pure CNTs and the number of dead cells on pure PP is less than one of on the PP added CNTs. It illustrated that the toxicity of CNTs influences the biocompatibility of the PP composites with osteoblasts cells. Compared the PP/MWCNTs with the PP/NH₂-SWCNT and PP/CS/MWCNT, the number of cells on PP/NH₂-SWCNT and PP/CS/MWCNT was more and bigger than one of the PP/MWCNTs, which demonstrated that the toxicity of functionalized CNTs were weaker than pure CNTs. In addition, we observed that the number of cells on PP/CS/MWCNT was more and more spreading than one of on PP/NH₂-SWCNT, which may be because the noncovalent functionalized MWCNTs with chitosan avoid destroying the structure of MWCNTs, while covalent functionalized SWCNTs with plasma NH₂ caused the defects on the surface structure of SWCNTs. The results demonstrated that noncovalent functionalized CNTs with CS may be more biocompatible than covalent functionalized CNTs.

Figure.6: CLSM micrographs showing the morphologies of human osteoblasts cultured on PP nanocomposites. (a) pure PP, (b) PP/MWCNT, (c) PP/NH₂-SWCNT, (d) PP/CS/MWCNT (Green stands for the living cells and red on behalf of the dead cells)

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we compared systematically the dispersion, tensile strength, E modulus and biocompatibility of six different modified CNTs and as-received CNTs (SWCNTs, SWCNTs with COOH, SWCNTs with NH₂, MWCNTs, MWCNTs with chitosan, MWCNTs with lysozyme) in PP matrix. The dispersions of six different CNTs in solvent were quantitatively analyzed via HSPs calculated by computer software we designed.

The dispersion of MWCNTs and MWCNTs noncovalently modified by chitosan (CS/MWCNTs) and lysozyme (LZ/MWCNTs) in solvents were characterized by ultraviolet and visible spectrophotometer (UV-Vis). And the calculated HSPs sphere clearly proved that the noncovalent modified MWCNTs with chitosan and lysozyme had more maximum tolerance than MWCNTs, especially is CS/MWCNTs. The dispersion of SWCNTs and SWCNTs covalently modified by plasma carboxylic acid (COOH-SWCNTs) and plasma amine (NH₂-SWCNTs) in solvents was investigated by dynamic light scattering (DLS). The results indicated that the HSP data of SWCNTs and COOH-SWCNTs and NH₂-SWCNTs was the same as DMF and the radius of HSPs sphere was 0.

The dispersions of the CNTs in polymers were observed by the confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM). Among all of PP composites, we observed that the dispersion of PP/SWCNTs is the worst, while the dispersion of PP/CS/MWCNTs is the best. In addition, we believed that the dispersion of CNTs in PP matrix was in accord with in solvents and HSPs of materials.

The mechanical property of PP were conducted by electronic tensile tester, we found that the tensile strength of PP with CNTs is higher than pure PP and the PP/CS/MWCNTs nanocomposites shown the largest E modulus, while the PP/NH₂-SWCNTs exerted the smallest E modulus. The tensile

strength and E modulus of PP composites was closely related with the dispersion of CNTs in PP. Covalent functionalized methods introduces defects into CNTs, which could lead to the decrease of mechanical properties, while the noncovalent functionalized methods can avoid the destruction of carbon nanotubes structure, which could contribute to the increase of E modulus of PP composites.

In biocompatibility test of PP composites, we found that the biocompatibility of the pure PP was better than one of the other PP added CNT. The biocompatibility of functionalized CNTs was better than the one without functionalization. PP composites with the noncovalent functionalized carbon nanotubes were more biocompatible than covalent functionalized carbon nanotubes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author gratefully acknowledges the support of K.C.Wong Education Foundation, Hong Kong. This work was also financially supported by a grant from Shanxi Province Science Foundation for Youths (Grant No. 2014021020-4) and National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No.51403150).

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Iijima, 'Helical Microtubules of Graphitic Carbon', *Nature*, **354**, 1991, 56-56.
- [2] A. Cassell, L. Delzeit, C. Nguyen, R. Stevens, J. Han, and M. Meyyappan, 'Carbon Nanotubes by Cvd and Applications', *Journal De Physique Iv*, **11**, 2001, 401-09.
- [3] M. Liebau, A. P. Graham, Z. Gabric, R. Seidel, E. Unger, G. S. Duesberg, and F. Kreupl, 'Electrical Interconnects Made of Carbon Nanotubes', in *Electronic Properties of Synthetic Nanostructures*, ed. by H. Kuzmany, J. Fink, M. Mehring and S. Roth (Melville: Amer Inst Physics, 2004), pp. 536-39.
- [4] C. Yu, Q. Hao, and L. Shi, 'Measuring Thermal and Thermoelectric Properties of Nanotubes and Nanobelts', in *Thermal Conductivity 27: Thermal Expansion 15*, ed. by H. Wang, W. D. Porter and G. Worley (Lancaster: Destech Publications, Inc, 2005), pp. 278-88.
- [5] Zhijing Zhang, Christina Dewan, Saumya Kothari, Saibal Mitra, and Dale Teeters, 'Carbon Nanotube Synthesis, Characteristics, and Microbattery Applications', *Materials Science and Engineering: B*, **116**, 2005, 363-68.
- [6] S. Gong, Z. H. Zhu, and S. A. Meguid, 'Carbon Nanotube Agglomeration Effect on Piezoresistivity of Polymer Nanocomposites', *Polymer*, **55**, 2014, 5488-99.
- [7] W. Wohlleben, M. W. Meier, S. Vogel, R. Landsiedel, G. Cox, S. Hirth, and Z. Tomovic, 'Elastic Cnt-Polyurethane Nanocomposite: Synthesis, Performance and Assessment of Fragments Released During Use', *Nanoscale*, **5**, 2013, 369-80.
- [8] Basit Yameen, Nicolas Zydziak, Steffen M. Weidner, Michael Bruns, and Christopher Barner-Kowollik, 'Conducting Polymer/Swcnts Modular Hybrid Materials Via Diels–Alder Ligation', *Macromolecules*, **46**, 2013, 2606-15.
- [9] Yue Zhou, Haiping Xu, Noa Lachman, Mehdi Ghaffari, Shan Wu, Yang Liu, Asli Ugur, Karen K. Gleason, Brian L. Wardle, and Q. M. Zhang, 'Advanced Asymmetric Supercapacitor Based on Conducting Polymer and Aligned Carbon Nanotubes with Controlled Nanomorphology', *Nano Energy*, **9**, 2014, 176-85.
- [10] V. Gayathri, and R. Geetha, 'Carbon Nanotube as Nems Sensor - Effect of Chirality and Stone-Wales Defect Intend', *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, **34**, 2006, 824-28.

- [11] C. K. M. Fung, M. Q. H. Zhang, R. H. M. Chan, W. J. Li, and Ieee, 'A Pmma-Based Micro Pressure Sensor Chip Using Carbon Nanotubes as Sensing Elements', in *Mems 2005 Miami: Technical Digest* (New York: Ieee, 2005), pp. 251-54.
- [12] S. Hwang, M. Batmunkh, M. J. Nine, H. Chung, and H. Jeong, 'Dye-Sensitized Solar Cell Counter Electrodes Based on Carbon Nanotubes', *Chemphyschem*, **16**, 2015, 53-65.
- [13] B. Adeniran, and R. Mokaya, 'Low Temperature Synthesized Carbon Nanotube Superstructures with Superior Co₂ and Hydrogen Storage Capacity', *Journal Of Materials Chemistry A*, **3**, 2015, 5148-61.
- [14] J. H. Zhang, J. B. Zang, J. J. Huang, Y. H. Wang, and G. X. Xin, 'Synthesis of an Architectural Electrode Based on Manganese Oxide and Carbon Nanotubes for Flexible Supercapacitors', *Materials Letters*, **126**, 2014, 24-27.
- [15] M. Chakrabarti, R. Kiseleva, A. Vertegel, and S. K. Ray, 'Carbon Nanomaterials for Drug Delivery and Cancer Therapy', *Journal Of Nanoscience And Nanotechnology*, **15**, 2015, 5501-11.
- [16] Jing Ma, and Raino Mikael Larsen, 'Effect of Surface Modification on the Hansen Solubility Parameters of Single-Walled Carbon Nanotubes', *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, **52**, 2013, 3514-21.
- [17] Florence Pannetier, Charles Vriamont, Béatrice Vanhorenbeke, Olivier Riant, and Sophie Hermans, 'Covalent Functionalization of Carbon Nanotubes with Xanthates and Peroxides', *European Journal of Organic Chemistry*, **2015**, 2015, 1804-10.
- [18] Zois Syrgiannis, Frank Hauke, Jonas Röhr, Martin Hundhausen, Ralf Graupner, Yiannis Elemes, and Andreas Hirsch, 'Covalent Sidewall Functionalization of Swnts by Nucleophilic Addition of Lithium Amides', *European Journal of Organic Chemistry*, **2008**, 2008, 2544-50.
- [19] Henry Kuo Feng Cheng, Yongzheng Pan, Nanda Gopal Sahoo, Kahwei Chong, Lin Li, Siew Hwa Chan, and Jianhong Zhao, 'Improvement in Properties of Multiwalled Carbon Nanotube/Polypropylene Nanocomposites through Homogeneous Dispersion with the Aid of Surfactants', *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **124**, 2012, 1117-27.
- [20] Eun Yub Choi, Sang Chul Roh, and C. K. Kim, 'Noncovalent Functionalization of Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes with Pyrene-Linked Nylon66 for High Performance Nylon66/Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotube Composites', *Carbon*, **72**, 2014, 160-68.
- [21] A. Di Crescenzo, V. Ettore, and A. Fontana, 'Non-Covalent and Reversible Functionalization of Carbon Nanotubes', *Beilstein J Nanotechnol*, **5**, 2014, 1675-90.
- [22] L. Vaisman, H. D. Wagner, and G. Marom, 'The Role of Surfactants in Dispersion of Carbon Nanotubes', *Adv Colloid Interface Sci*, **128-130**, 2006, 37-46.
- [23] Howard Wang, 'Dispersing Carbon Nanotubes Using Surfactants', *Current Opinion in Colloid & Interface Science*, **14**, 2009, 364-71.
- [24] Ke Zhang, Ying Dan Liu, and Hyoung Jin Choi, 'Surfactant Effect on Functionalized Carbon Nanotube Coated Snowman-Like Particles and Their Electro-Responsive Characteristics', *Materials Research Bulletin*, **47**, 2012, 2752-55.
- [25] H. T. Ham, Y. S. Choi, and I. J. Chung, 'An Explanation of Dispersion States of Single-Walled Carbon Nanotubes in Solvents and Aqueous Surfactant Solutions Using Solubility Parameters', *J Colloid Interface Sci*, **286**, 2005, 216-23.
- [26] Håne Launay, Charles M. Hansen, and Kristoffer Almdal, 'Hansen Solubility Parameters for a Carbon Fiber/Epoxy Composite', *Carbon*, **45**, 2007, 2859-65.
- [27] Jing Ma, and Lelai Zhou, 'A New Procedure for Calculating Hansen Solubility Parameters of Carbon Nanotube/Polymer Composites', *Polymer Bulletin*, **68**, 2011, 1053-63.

- [28] A. S. Campbell, C. Dong, F. Meng, J. Hardinger, G. Perhinschi, N. Wu, and C. Z. Dinu, 'Enzyme Catalytic Efficiency: A Function of Bio-Nano Interface Reactions', *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces*, **6**, 2014, 5393-403.
- [29] A. Fonseca-Garcia, J. D. Mota-Morales, I. A. Quintero-Ortega, Z. Y. Garcia-Carvajal, V. Martinez-Lopez, E. Ruvalcaba, C. Landa-Solis, L. Solis, C. Ibarra, M. C. Gutierrez, M. Terrones, I. C. Sanchez, F. del Monte, M. C. Velasquillo, and G. Luna-Barcenas, 'Effect of Doping in Carbon Nanotubes on the Viability of Biomimetic Chitosan-Carbon Nanotubes-Hydroxyapatite Scaffolds', *J Biomed Mater Res A*, **102**, 2014, 3341-51.
- [30] Jeongwoo Lee, Myunghun Kim, Chang Kook Hong, and Sang Eun Shim, 'Measurement of the Dispersion Stability of Pristine and Surface-Modified Multiwalled Carbon Nanotubes in Various Nonpolar and Polar Solvents', *Measurement Science and Technology*, **18**, 2007, 3707-12.
- [31] Ji Hoon Lee, Man Tea Kim, Kyong Yop Rhee, and Soo Jin Park, 'An Experimental Investigation on the Conductive Behavior of Carbon Nanotube-Reinforced Natural Polymer Nanocomposites', *Research on Chemical Intermediates*, **40**, 2014, 2487-93.
- [32] Z. F. Li, G. H. Luo, W. P. Zhou, F. Wei, R. Xiang, and Y. P. Liu, 'The Quantitative Characterization of the Concentration and Dispersion of Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes in Suspension by Spectrophotometry', *Nanotechnology*, **17**, 2006, 3692-98.
- [33] T. I. T. Okpalugo, P. Papakonstantinou, H. Murphy, J. McLaughlin, and N. M. D. Brown, 'High Resolution Xps Characterization of Chemical Functionalised Mwcnts and Swcnts', *Carbon*, **43**, 2005, 153-61.
- [34] K. D. Patel, T. H. Kim, E. J. Lee, C. M. Han, J. Y. Lee, R. K. Singh, and H. W. Kim, 'Nanostructured Biointerfacing of Metals with Carbon Nanotube/Chitosan Hybrids by Electrodeposition for Cell Stimulation and Therapeutics Delivery', *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces*, **6**, 2014, 20214-24.
- [35] A. Ameli, P. U. Jung, and C. B. Park, 'Electrical Properties and Electromagnetic Interference Shielding Effectiveness of Polypropylene/Carbon Fiber Composite Foams', *Carbon*, **60**, 2013, 379-91.
- [36] G. S. Ezat, A. L. Kelly, S. C. Mitchell, M. Youseffi, and P. D. Coates, 'Effect of Maleic Anhydride Grafted Polypropylene Compatibilizer on the Morphology and Properties of Polypropylene/Multiwalled Carbon Nanotube Composite', *Polymer Composites*, **33**, 2012, 1376-86.
- [37] N. Gamze Karsli, Sertan Yesil, and Ayse Aytac, 'Effect of Hybrid Carbon Nanotube/Short Glass Fiber Reinforcement on the Properties of Polypropylene Composites', *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **63**, 2014, 154-60.
- [38] Cristhian Garzón, and Humberto Palza, 'Electrical Behavior of Polypropylene Composites Melt Mixed with Carbon-Based Particles: Effect of the Kind of Particle and Annealing Process', *Composites Science and Technology*, **99**, 2014, 117-23.
- [39] Myung-Sun Hong, Woong-Ki Choi, Kay-Hyeok An, Shin-Jae Kang, Soo-Jin Park, Young Sil Lee, and Byung-Joo Kim, 'Electromagnetic Interference Shielding Behaviors of Carbon Fibers-Reinforced Polypropylene Matrix Composites: Ii. Effects of Filler Length Control', *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry*, **20**, 2014, 3901-04.
- [40] K. S. Khare, F. Khabaz, and R. Khare, 'Effect of Carbon Nanotube Functionalization on Mechanical and Thermal Properties of Cross-Linked Epoxy-Carbon Nanotube Nanocomposites: Role of Strengthening the Interfacial Interactions', *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces*, **6**, 2014, 6098-110.

- [41] Yuling Ma, Daming Wu, Ying Liu, Xiaofeng Li, Hui Qiao, and Zhong-Zhen Yu, 'Electrically Conductive and Super-Tough Polypropylene/Carbon Nanotube Nanocomposites Prepared by Melt Compounding', *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **56**, 2014, 384-91.
- [42] Y. Ngabonziza, J. Li, and C. F. Barry, 'Electrical Conductivity and Mechanical Properties of Multiwalled Carbon Nanotube-Reinforced Polypropylene Nanocomposites', *Acta Mechanica*, **220**, 2011, 289-98.
- [43] M. Nurul, and M. Mariatti, 'Effect of Thermal Conductive Fillers on the Properties of Polypropylene Composites', *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, **26**, 2011, 627-39.
- [44] Humberto Palza, Boris Reznik, Manfred Wilhelm, Oscar Arias, and Alejandro Vargas, 'Electrical, Thermal, and Mechanical Characterization of Poly(Propylene)/Carbon Nanotube/Clay Hybrid Composite Materials', *Macromolecular Materials and Engineering*, **297**, 2012, 474-80.
- [45] R. Ansari, S. Ajori, and S. Rouhi, 'Structural and Elastic Properties and Stability Characteristics of Oxygenated Carbon Nanotubes under Physical Adsorption of Polymers', *Applied Surface Science*, **332**, 2015, 640-47.
- [46] Mohammad Eskandari, Seyed Hassan Hosseini, Mohsen Adeli, and Ali Pourjavadi, 'Polymer-Functionalized Carbon Nanotubes in Cancer Therapy: A Review', *Iranian Polymer Journal*, **23**, 2014, 387-403.
- [47] Zhenzhen Gao, Hao Tong, Jianhui Chen, Shihong Yue, Wenlong Bai, Xiaogang Zhang, Yanfei Pan, Ming Shi, and Yuxiang Song, 'Preparation and Supercapacitive Performance of Polyaniline Covalently Grafted Carbon Nanotubes Composite Material', *Acta Chimica Sinica*, **72**, 2014, 1175.
- [48] Hyeong Taek Ham, Yeong Suk Choi, Mu Guen Chee, and In Jae Chung, 'Singlewall Carbon Nanotubes Covered with Polystyrene Nanoparticles Byin-Situ Miniemulsion Polymerization', *Journal of Polymer Science Part A: Polymer Chemistry*, **44**, 2006, 573-84.
- [49] S. Manivannan, Il Ok Jeong, Je Hwang Ryu, Chang Seok Lee, Ki Seo Kim, Jin Jang, and Kyu Chang Park, 'Dispersion of Single-Walled Carbon Nanotubes in Aqueous and Organic Solvents through a Polymer Wrapping Functionalization', *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics*, **20**, 2008, 223-29.
- [50] 1 Nguyen Thi Thu Trang Nguyen Thuy Chinh, 1 Dinh Thi Mai Thanh, 1 To Thi Xuan Hang, 1, and 1 Pham Minh Quan Nguyen Vu Giang, 2 Nguyen Tien Dung, 3 Thai Hoang, 1, '<Thermal Property, Morphology, and Hydrolysis Ability Of poly(Lactic Acid)_Chitosan Nanocomposites Using Polyethylene Oxide.Pdf>', *Applied polymer*, **132**, 2015.
- [51] YF (Zhan Zhan, Yingfei)[1,2] ; Zeng, W (Zeng, Wen)[1] ; Jiang, GX (Jiang, Guoxia)[1] ; Wang, Q (Wang, Qun)[3,4] ; Shi, XW (Shi, Xiaowen)[1] ; Zhou, ZH (Zhou, Zhehao)[1] ; Deng, HB (Deng, Hongbing)[1] ; Du, YM (Du, Yumin)[1], '<Construction of Lysozyme Exfoliated Rectorite-Based Electrospun nanofibrous Membranes for Bacterial Inhibition.Pdf>', *Applied polymer*, **132**, 2015.